

Decoupling from Chinese Technology? Navigating Current Trends in Chinese-European Service Relations

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Abstract

Design/methodology/approach: Applying input-output models, the study showed the growing role of China as a supplier of ICT services to European manufacturing. It also identified the industries that are most dependent on Chinese ICT services.

Purpose: The article focuses on cross-sectoral analysis concerning services, especially ICT services, flowing from China to European manufacturing. The aim of the study is to analyse Sino-European relations in terms of ICT servicification. The article attempts to answer the following questions: Does China's relationship with Europe in terms of servicification of manufacturing align with global servicification trends? Have global economic shocks, such as decoupling policies, diminished the flows of Chinese ICT services in European advanced manufacturing sectors?

Findings: The analysis highlights the increasing reliance of European manufacturing on Chinese ICT services, with a notable rise across both Western Europe and CEE. This dependency is particularly strong in advanced sectors such as automotive and electronics, and there is no evidence of decoupling from China, even amidst global shocks or geopolitical tensions like the Trump presidency. Additionally, the BRI had limited direct impact, as the servicification trends appear driven more by broader globalization processes.

Originality/value: the study investigates all European countries and their manufacturing sectors' reliance on Chinese services. It concentrates on services related to high technology, specifically ICT. Moreover, the previous research has focused on total servicification of manufacturing, in general, neglecting industry-specific analysis. It contributes to the literature by providing insights into relationships between developing economies and developed ones in terms of GVCs in digital servicification and decoupling conditions.

(Studies focused on cross-sectoral connections between China and Europe have some disadvantages. Firstly, they did not investigate all European countries) and their manufacturing sectors' reliance on Chinese services. Secondly, none of the studies concentrated on services related to high technology, specifically ICT. All of them focused on total services rather than classifying them according to their level of sophistication. Thirdly, previous research has focused on total servicification of manufacturing, in general, neglecting industry-specific

analysis. This study aims to address these gaps and contributes to empirical studies in the field of cross-sectoral value-added flows.)

Keywords: servicification of manufacturing, ICT services, global value chains, manufacturing industry, China, Europe

JEL: F10, F14

Competing interests

The author declares there is no conflict of interests.

Funding

The article is the result of the research project ‘Digital Silk Road as a network of technological connections between China and Europe within value chains: towards win-win or decoupling?’ financed by the National Science Centre, Poland (UMO-2021/43/B/HS4/01079).

1. Introduction

Global value chains (GVCs) have undergone significant structural transformations in recent years which call "servicification"¹ and risk of “decoupling”². Servicification denotes the increasing role of service sectors in GVC processes and the growing importance of services in manufacturing activities, resulting in firms becoming more dependent on services. According to Nano and Stolzenburg (2021) service sectors support manufacturing by serving as critical inputs in both production and exports (servicification of manufacturing), and service sectors establish their own GVCs, where certain services can be fragmented similarly to manufacturing (service-based GVCs). Nowadays, digital servicification spreads. It involves the use of digital technology to integrate services into existing products, creating added value for customers, and improving operational efficiency (Ginting et al., 2024). Decoupling, in other hands, means weakening connections between economies across various dimensions, including economic, political, and cultural realms (Witt et al, 2021). This process has accelerated since Trump’s presidency and trade war.

Research has consistently shown that the share of services in value-added trade is both substantial and growing. The rise in digital service participation in GVCs can be attributed to

¹ According to WTO data, around 70 per cent of global trade is conducted through GVCs, while an increasing proportion of this trade is in services, including the growing role of advanced ones (Xing et al., 2023).

² It is assumed that the decoupling process started with the presidency of Donald Trump and his policy towards China.

services like information and communication technology (ICT), which enhance firm performance and stimulates improvements in economies positions in global economy. China is also part of these trends, having established itself in manufacturing GVCs and now seeking to strengthen its position in service GVCs (Su et al. 2021; Cieřlik, 2024a). At the same time, traditional GVCs are proving to be less and less important as the role of the economy in the world is increasingly determined by advanced industries and services. Therefore, China is intensifying its efforts to strengthen its position in technological GVCs, including digital service GVCs in developed countries (Ambos et al., 2021). This led to the formulation of the first research question:

- Does China's relationship with Europe in terms of servicification of manufacturing align with global servicification trends?

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and the Digital Silk Road (DSR)³ are part of global trends related to digital servicification. Furthermore, these strategies align with the ongoing 4.0 and 5.0 industrial revolution (Ali et al., 2022; Ammiratto et al., 2023) and Chinese strategy of technological catching up (Li et al., 2020; Castello Esquerdo et al. 2023). However, a number of issues have emerged that could disrupt this process. Investment and trade treaty networks and their effectiveness may be considered in this context (Chaisse and Kirkwood, 2020). The suspended negotiations over the introduction of the Comprehensive Agreement on Investment (CAI) also aligns into this narrative. These have highlighted differences in perceptions of economic cooperation between China and the EU (Burnay and Raube, 2022; Huang and Qi, 2022; Fach Gómez, 2021). This coincided with (and was also partly the result of) increased US activity intending to decouple with China. Decoupling sentiment has also been noticeable in Europe (Felbermayr, 2021). These activities might have resulted in changes in trade channels, particularly in technological goods and services (Bown, 2020; Bo et al., 2022). Hence, it seems reasonable to investigate whether there have been changes in the inflows of Chinese technology services to developed countries as a result of these disruptions. This led to the formulation of the second research question:

- Have global economic shocks, such as decoupling policies, diminished the flows of Chinese ICT services in European advanced manufacturing sectors?

The aim of the study is to analyse Sino-European relations in terms of ICT (digital) servicification. The study is empirical. It contributes to the literature by providing insights into

³ It is a long-term technology plan, Beijing has been supporting its exporters, including technology companies, and fostering technological cooperation with selected countries.

relationships between developing economies and developed ones in terms of GVCs in digital servicification and decoupling conditions.

The study was limited to the servicification of manufacturing in 1995-2020. 31 European economies, perceived in geographical terms, were chosen for two reasons. Firstly, Europe is one of the most important developed regions as a recipient of Chinese services. Secondly, it is also partly considering a decoupling plan from China. The focus on ICT services is explained in detail in the "Context of the study" section. ICT services are understood according to the OECD's classification and consist of publishing, audiovisual and broadcasting activities, telecommunications, and computer programming, consultancy, and information services activities.

The paper is divided into five sections, including the introduction and conclusions. The "Literature review" introduces the concept of links between services and production. Then the context of the topic was presented. It is followed by a brief description of the research method. Section fourth examines the study results. In the conclusions, the research questions and implications of the study are discussed.

2. Literature review

Although services are a key part of global manufacturing and international trade, their role in GVCs has received limited attention. Links between manufacturing and services are included in the debate on deindustrialization (Juhasz et al., 2023; Gong et al., 2022) and mentioned above servicification of manufacturing. Manufacturing often relies on activities from non-manufacturing sectors, such as domestically or internationally sourced services. Traditionally, manufacturing was seen as solely contributing to its own value-added, with little attention to its links with other industries. However, recent approaches highlight the importance of services throughout all stages of production, suggesting that manufacturing involves a combination of activities, including services, along the value chain (Gölgeci et al., 2021). This integration of services in manufacturing is known as mentioned above "servicification." Services like R&D are used in early stages, while ICT services are essential at various stages, including maintenance and repair, making them critical across the entire production process.

Studies have shown that servicification contributes to the optimization of production systems and the improvement of product quality. For example, Lodefalk (2017) emphasizes that integrating advanced services such as digital technologies, R&D, and design into manufacturing processes leads to improved quality control and product innovation, which are

essential for maintaining competitiveness in global markets. Similarly, Crozet and Milet (2017) in their work found that firms adopting servicification not only enhance their production quality but also experience increased productivity and market differentiation. The incorporation of ICT services allows for real-time monitoring and adjustment of production processes, which directly impacts the consistency and quality of the output. These findings align with the broader consensus in the literature that servicification is a key driver of quality enhancement in manufacturing, enabling firms to respond more flexibly and efficiently to market demands (Low and Pasadilla, 2016).

While many studies have explored the significance of cross-sectoral relationships, most have not been international (e.g. Li et al., 2024a; Dai et al., 2024; Pattnayak and Chadha, 2022; Reddy and Sasidharan, 2022; Hansen et al., 2022; Beverelli et al., 2016). Participation in the global economy implies cross-sectoral overlaps on an international scale. However, the impact of services on manufacturing exports has not been extensively studied. A few studies from the last decade have addressed this issue (e.g. Miroudot and Cadestin, 2017; Heuser and Matto, 2017; Liu et al., 2018; Pezzotta et al., 2022; Verhoef et al., 2021; Blázquez et al., 2020; Díaz-Mora et al., 2022; Matthess and Kunkel, 2020).

A complex approach to the globalization of servicification provided studies by Beerepoot et al. (2017), Miroudot and Cadestin (2017) and Kleibert (2016). Hing and Thangavelu (2023), Fedyunina et al. (2024) and Chun et al. (2021) analysed firms productivity and cost-efficiency in servicification. There are also studies focused on connections between trade and open-up policy and servicification (e.g. Kim, 2019; Atolia et al., 2018; Miroudot, 2017).

In the context of the article, the literature on servicification in China is particularly relevant. Unfortunately, there has been only a small number of studies so far.

Du and Agbola (2024) showed that factors like FDI and capital intensity improved through production links, although China's growing global market share reduced the influence of foreign-servicified manufacturing firms. Chen et al. (2023) identified a similar need for restructuring. Their study proved that if manufacturing servitisation increases, regional services development improves manufacturing firm productivity. Similar findings provided Zhu et al. (2023). Sun and Xi (2024) and Li et al. (2024b) investigated the great role of digitalization in Chinese GVCs. In turn Chen et al. (2024) proved the role of AI in this process. Guo et al. (2021) emphasized the critical role of investment servicification, while Zhang et al. (2023) highlighted the varied impacts of different servicification types on firm performance. Liu and Hua (2024) investigated role of servicification in allocation efficiency. Studies like those by Chen et al.

(2021, 2022) and Liu and Kim (2020) demonstrated the importance of service sectors, particularly in industries like telecom and IT. Huang et al. (2024) proved that servicification may “directly promote the international competitiveness of China's manufacturing based on the domestic value added of exports, and the improvement of international competitiveness will interact with the centralization of network power status”. Similar Liu et al. (2024) investigated Internet platforms in China and proved that servicification is vital for their competitiveness and financial performance. Liao et al. (2022) showed the need for fixed configurations to enable GVC transitions in Chinese manufacturing. Digitalization, as studied by Wenxiao and Thangavelu (2024) and Xing et al. (2023), was found to be essential in improving manufacturing servicification and innovation performance. Finally, Xiao et al. (2024) linked digital economy policies at the city level to enterprise digital transformation in listed Chinese firms. All these studies focused on the internal servicification of manufacturing and did not address international flows. Furthermore, a fundamental flaw of most of the studies cited above (with the exception of the work of Liu et al, 2024; Wenxiao and Thangavelu, 2024; Xing et al, 2023; Xiao et al, 2024) was their treatment of servicification in general, without considering different types of services.

There are only a few internationally oriented studies about China itself. Qiao et al. (2024) investigated the role of servicification in natural environment protection in exports context. Natanelov et al. (2022) found how advanced services (blockchain) could affect value chains. Menghu (2023) and Zhu (2023) proved that servicification has an impact on the quality of Chinese exports.

There are more studies where China is among other analysed economies. Yu et al. (2022) applied panel data from 44 countries and 18 industries spanning 14 years and matched the global input–output database with micro-level data from Chinese manufacturing firms and found a positive effect of imported producer service inputs on domestic manufacturing exports. Similar research proposed Wang et al. (2024). They applied panel data covering 43 economies and found that higher levels of manufacturing servicification and service trade openness lead to higher TFP in the manufacturing industry. Kan et al. (2022) argued that generally digitalization may upgrade China’s position in GVCs. More specifically, Gao and Rong (2023) proved that servicification is one of the most important ways to upgrade the role of Chinese companies in GVCs. A boarder study was carried out by Fan et al. (2024) . They applied data from 17 manufacturing industries in 65 regions for 2000–2018 and investigated the impact of digital transformation in services on the participation of manufacturing industries in GVCs. They proved that by reducing trade costs and improving production efficiency in manufacturing

industries, digitalization of services can significantly promote manufacturing GVC participation. A comparable study was carried out by Bian and Fan (2024).

There are also studies on servicification in China that analyse the problem interdisciplinarily and indirectly address GVCs. For example, Mishra and Valencia (2023) examine the issue of foreign trade in digital services and digital inclusion, showing legal solutions introduced by Asian countries that Europe could use. Marcoux and Sylvestre-Fleury (2022), on the other hand, analyse issues related to public procurement.

The aforementioned studies have a few limitations. Firstly, they did not investigate all European countries and their manufacturing sectors' reliance on Chinese services. Secondly, none of the studies concentrated on services related to high technology, specifically ICT and its subsectors. All of them focused on total services rather than classifying them according to their level of sophistication. Thirdly, previous research has focused on total servicification of manufacturing, in general, neglecting industry-specific analysis. This study aims to address these gaps and contributes to empirical studies in the field of cross-sectoral value-added flows.

2. Context of the study

Within the realm of service trades, the significance of ICT service trade has been on the rise compared to other service types (UNCTAD, 2021; Chanda, 2017). Furthermore, there is a worldwide trend towards an increasing role for services in ICT in gross exports and imports. Europe plays a very important role in services, both on the export and import side. At the same time, a growing role for Asia is observed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Regional trends in shares of ICT services in gross exports and imports 1995-2020

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

Recent research (Xing et al., 2023; Liu and Li, 2022; UNCTAD, 2024) underscores the significance of the servicification of manufacturing activities within the GVCs in general. The same tendency we observe in China, where services outperforms manufacturing in terms of GVC forwardness. The position of ICT services is also improving, especially after introduction the BRI (Figure 2). At the same time, changes are being observed in Chinese output and inter-sectoral connections. Analyzing domestic output, it is noted that the share of services in manufacturing has increased significantly in recent years (Figure 3). Moreover, ICT services play an important role in domestic manufacturing both in China and Europe. However, in

Europe this activity has experienced dynamic growth recently. The deceleration of the servicification of domestic manufacturing by ICT in China, together with the increasing forwardness of ICT, may indicate a redirection of Chinese ICT services to GVCs (Figure 2, Figure 4). These findings are consistent with the research conducted by Du and Agbola (2024), Huang et al. (2024), Chen et al. (2023) and Guo et al. (2018).

Figure 2. Chinese type of participation in GVCs in 1995-2020 (forwardness)

Forwardness is calculated on the basis of (Borin et al., 2021). If the indices are higher than 0, then the economy occupies forward position in GVCs.

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

Figure 3. Servicification of Chinese manufacturing's gross exports and final demand from 1995 to 2020 (% of total flows of value added to manufacturing)

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

Figure 4. ICT servicification of domestic manufacturing in China and Europe in 1995-2020 (% of domestic manufacturing)

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

When it comes to Chinese technological strategies, ICT services are an important channel for influencing the production of other countries. ICT has become a crucial component of infrastructure connectivity due to its increasing use for connectivity purposes. ICT service import from China is expected to increase as a channel to achieve a higher ICT development, not only in less technologically advanced economies. Empirical analysis shows that China's export to its trade partners (including Europe) has increased over the last decade, especially in capital-intensive industries (Yu et al., 2020).

Chinese cooperation with Europe in ICT service derives from following reasons. ICT services have played a crucial role in European production and trade (UNCTAD, 2024). In 2020, the value added by the EU's ICT sector was equivalent to 5.2% of GDP (Eurostat, 2024). On the other hand, we observe a decrease in domestic ICT services flows to European manufacturing (OECD, 2024). This implies growth in foreign ICT services flows, including Chinese services hypothetically. Ghodsi et al. (2021) carefully analyzed the condition of the ICT sector in Europe about the most important players in the market (e.g. U.S., China, India etc.). Similar conclusions were drawn from the study by Gordon and Sayed (2020), who argue that "...post-2005 slowdown is consistent with the broader view that ongoing innovation has been less potent in boosting productivity growth compared to earlier decades..." Both research found that Europe is no longer able to increase its capacity in ICT, unlike China. This may lead to the transfer of some manufacturing competencies by European companies to Chinese

companies, which may result in increased inflows of Chinese value added from ICT services, and thus greater shares of China among the suppliers of such value added. Hence, an examination of changes in China's share of European manufacturing seems justified.

In addition to the empirical rationale for the study, the study offers some theoretical contributions on GVCs. As the study focuses on China's role in GVCs, it could benefit from deeper engagement with the GVC framework. Recent literature emphasizes the role of digitalization in reshaping GVCs, which is relevant to the analysis of China's increasing digital servicification (Lee and Gereffi, 2021; Huang et al. 2024). The concept of servicification is also visible in studies investigate how technological advancements lead to the integration of services into manufacturing processes (Gopalan et al., 2022; Gölgeci et al., 2021). Another theoretical area that can expand the research conducted in the article is the adaptation of modern technologies to the economy, in this case to manufacturing. Studies by Urbach et al. (2017), Ghobakhloo (2020) or Mohapatra et al. (2022) show this adaptation both in crisis conditions (COVID-19) and as a natural stage of economic development. The study of relationships between economies may also refer to the technology dependency theory (Se Gregori, 1978; Norman et al., 2023).

3. Methodology

To determine the participation and status of the analyzed economies in GVCs, as well as the flows of value added between Chinese services and European manufacturing, a value-added model was developed. It included value added in industries/sectors. The Leontief input-output model was used as a basic approach. The balance equations system in the input-output model for a single economy was modified to suit a multi-economy model. This model is grounded on the decomposition of gross exports. Then it was developed by several authors: (e.g. Timmer et al., 2012; Johnson and Noguera, 2012; Koopman et al., 2014; Los et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2013). The method provides estimates of total value added in GVCs and performs calculations at the cross-sectoral flows, including the servicification of manufacturing.

Three methods were considered for the study: Wang et al. (2013), Koopman et al. (2014), and Los et al. (2016), all using input-output tables to decompose value added in trade. Wang et al. (2013) focused on bilateral/industry-level export decomposition, while Koopman et al. (2014) extended this by including intermediate goods/services. Los et al. (2016) used a 'hypothetical extraction method' to measure sector impacts on exports from a final demand perspective. Although differing in focus, all approaches provide insights into value-added analysis in GVCs.

Taking into account the benefits and limitations of the approaches by authors pointed above, the Wang et al. (2013) method was selected as it was deemed adequate for the study's needs. The authors have incorporated sectoral specialization into the methodology, allowing for a detailed examination of value-added flows across both domestic and foreign dimensions within individual sectors. This approach is particularly critical for analyzing the servicification of manufacturing. The method distinguishes between various streams of servicification, enabling a more nuanced understanding of this process (Figure 5). Foreign services value-added in manufacturing sector was the key element analysed in this article.

Figure 5. Servicification of manufacturing in gross exports

Source: own elaboration on Wang et al. (2013).

The methodology is predicated on the premise that within each economy, there exist S sectors/industries encompassing N economies. Each sector/industry is dedicated to the production of a distinct differentiated good. Production serves the dual purpose of satisfying final demand and generating intermediate goods (semi-finished products), which subsequently find utility in subsequent stages of product fabrication, both domestically and internationally.

$$X_i (s) = \sum_j y_{ij} (s) + \sum_j \sum_t z_{ij} (s, t),$$

where we define the coefficients matrix A as a matrix of dimension SNxSN, with elements

$$a_{ij} (s, t) = z_{ij} (s,t)/x_j (t)$$

Thus, the basic condition was formulated

$$x = (I - A)^{-1}y$$

Which can be represented in the form of the following matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ \vdots \\ X_N \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} I - A_{11} & \cdots & -A_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -A_{N1} & \cdots & I - A_{NN} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \sum_i^N Y_{1j} \\ \vdots \\ \sum_i^N Y_{Nj} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{11} & \cdots & Z_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ Z_{N1} & \cdots & Z_{NN} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} Y_1 \\ \vdots \\ Y_N \end{bmatrix}$$

The matrix can be transformed into the following input-output model:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_{11} & \cdots & X_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{N1} & \cdots & X_{NN} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{11} & \cdots & Z_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ Z_{N1} & \cdots & Z_{NN} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Y_{11} & \cdots & Y_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ Y_{N1} & \cdots & Y_{NN} \end{bmatrix}$$

Where, in this model, there are N countries and S sectors. In this context, Z represents an SNxSN matrix, while X and Y are SNxN matrices.

Z - means gross production in the *i* economy that is needed to meet the final demand in the economy *j*

X - output produced in the *i* country that is absorbed by the market of country *j*

Y - output produced in the *i* country that is consumed by the country *j*

A value-added production matrix $\hat{V}\hat{V}ZY$ was then formulated

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{V}_1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & \hat{V}_N \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_{11} & \cdots & X_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{N1} & \cdots & X_{NN} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{V}_1 \sum_j^N Z_{1j} Y_{j1} & \cdots & \hat{V}_1 \sum_j^N Z_{1j} Y_{jN} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \hat{V}_N \sum_j^N Z_{Nj} Y_{j1} & \cdots & \hat{V}_N \sum_j^N Z_{Nj} Y_{jN} \end{bmatrix}$$

The diagonal matrix represents the value added of production that has been retained within the country, whereas the elements outside the diagonal matrix represent the value added that has been absorbed by the rest of the world (value added embodied in the gross exports of the trading partner).

$$VAExports_i = \sum_{j \neq i}^N V X_{ij} = V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N \sum_{n=1}^N Z_{in} Y_{nj} = V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ii} Y_{ij} + V_i \sum_{j \neq 1}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jj} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N \sum_{t \neq ij}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt}$$

Where:

$V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ii} Y_{ij}$ is the value added embodied in gross exports of final goods

$V_i \sum_{j \neq 1}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jj}$ is the value added embodied in gross exports of intermediate goods (semi-finished products)

$V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N \sum_{t \neq ij}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt}$ is indirect value added embodied in gross exports.

In order to formulate the share of value added coming from abroad in the gross export of the analyzed country, the following notation must be used:

$$VS = \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_j Z_{ji} E_{i*} = \sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} Y_{ij} + \sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} A_{ij} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} Y_{jj} + \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} E_{j*}$$

Where:

$\sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} Y_{ij}$ – is foreign value added included in gross exports of final goods

$\sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} A_{ij} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} Y_{jj}$ – is foreign value added included in gross exports of intermediate goods

$\sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} E_{j*}$ - is the double-calculated value added of intermediate goods produced abroad.

Finally, the export of intermediate goods that is used as an input to the production of goods abroad can be written as follows:

$$VSI = V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ji} E_{i*} = V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt} + V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ij} A_{jt} X_t + V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{ji} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ji} X_i$$

Where:

$V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt}$ – is indirect value added embodied in gross exports.

$V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ij} A_{jt} X_t$ – is the export of intermediate goods that will be used abroad to produce gross exports of intermediate goods

$V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{ji}$ – is domestic value added that returns to the country in the form of final products

$V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ji} X_i$ – is the domestic value added returned through imports of intermediate goods

Finally, the decomposition of gross exports can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DCP} = & [V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ii} Y_{ij} + V_i \sum_{j \neq 1}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jj} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N \sum_{t \neq ij}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt}] + [\sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} Y_{ij} + \\ & \sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} A_{ij} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} Y_{jj} + \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} E_{j*}] + [V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{ji} + \\ & V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ji} (I - A_{ii})^{-1} Y_{ii} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{jt} (I - A_{ii})^{-1} E_{i*} \end{aligned}$$

The above formulas can be explained as follows:

$V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ii} Y_{ij} + V_i \sum_{j \neq 1}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jj} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N \sum_{t \neq ij}^N Z_{ij} Y_{jt}$ and $V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} Y_{ji} + V_i \sum_{t \neq ij}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{ji} (I - A_{ii})^{-1} Y_{ii} + V_i \sum_{j \neq i}^N Z_{ij} A_{jt} (I - A_{ii})^{-1} E_{i*}$ - domestic value added embodied in the trading partner's gross exports (IVA)

$\sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} Y_{ij} + \sum_{t \neq i}^N \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} A_{ij} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} Y_{jj} + \sum_{j \neq i}^N V_t Z_{ti} (I - A_{jj})^{-1} E_{j*}$ - foreign value added embodied in a country's gross exports (FVA).

The formulas provided for calculating domestic value added embodied in the gross exports of partner countries and foreign value added embodied in the gross exports of the country also facilitate the assessment of the country's connections with foreign nations. In this context, the first formula represents the forward linkages or forward participation in GVCs, while the second formula can be associated with the backward linkages or participation. This study focuses on foreign value added.

In this study, ICT services were categorized based on the OECD's ISIC Revision 4 (2023 edition). The input-output model used for breaking down gross exports was applied to analyze cross-sectoral linkages between economies. Although the ICIO database covers a shorter time span compared to the MRIO developed by the Asian Development Bank, the decision to use the ICIO database was driven by two main factors: it includes data for all relevant economies;

the classification of industries within ICIO includes ICT services, which are not distinctly identified in the MRIO database.

4. Results

4.1. Servicification of total manufacturing

Chinese servicification of European manufacturing has been steadily increasing (Su et al., 2021). While Western Europe historically had a significantly higher share of Chinese services embedded in its manufacturing gross exports compared to CEE, recent years have seen a notable acceleration of Chinese service inflows into CEE. As a result, both European regions have become similarly dependent on Chinese services. The growth in Chinese service inflows into European manufacturing has shown significant fluctuations, largely driven by global economic shocks, such as the pandemic and the 2008 financial crisis. It is difficult to see sudden changes in Chinese service shares following the introduction of BRI or the US announcement of the decoupling process (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Chinese servicification of European manufacturing in 1995-2020

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

Among the industries particularly heavily dependent on Chinese ICT services in 2020. (above 10%), 6 industries can be identified (Table 1). The computer, electronic and optical

products were characterized by the largest increase in shares since 1995. In general, none of the subsectors of manufacturing recorded declines in the shares of Chinese ICT services.

Table 1. Chinese ICT services in European manufacturing by industry in 1995 and 2020 (% of gross exports)

	1995	2020	Change between 2020 and 1995
food products; beverages and tobacco products	1,68%	5,06%	3,38%
textiles, wearing apparel, leather and related products	5,33%	12,58%	7,25%
wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; articles of straw and plaiting materials	2,49%	9,54%	7,05%
paper and paper products; printing and reproduction of recorded media	1,96%	9,42%	7,46%
chemicals and non-metallic mineral products	2,26%	4,62%	2,36%
coke and refined petroleum products	1,42%	5,25%	3,83%
chemicals and pharmaceuticals	2,34%	4,21%	1,87%
rubber and plastics products	2,87%	7,95%	5,08%
other non-metallic mineral products	2,12%	7,66%	5,54%
basic metals	1,82%	7,42%	5,60%
fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	2,59%	8,95%	6,36%
computer, electronic and optical products	2,23%	15,98%	13,75%
electrical equipment	2,90%	13,31%	10,41%
machinery and equipment n.e.c.	2,82%	10,71%	7,89%
motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	2,89%	10,25%	7,36%
other transport equipment	3,43%	10,25%	6,82%
furniture; jewellery, musical instruments, toys, etc.; repair and installation of machinery and equipment	2,78%	7,94%	5,16%

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

The intensity of the influx of Chinese ICT services to European manufacturing resulted from the confluence of factors favorable for China: the debt crisis in the eurozone, the fall in the euro exchange rate and deindustrialization processes in Europe (especially Western Europe). At that time, China's internationalization and economic advancement strategies involving the acquisition of technology companies in developed countries strongly intensified. Hence, it can be concluded that the inflows of Chinese value added from ICT could be also related to Chinese investments and trade with Europe (Rhodium Group, 2023).

When analyzing European economies in the concept of servicification of manufacturing with ICT services in 1995-2020, we observed that all economies increased their dependence on Chinese ICT services. For most of the period, CEE outperformed Western Europe in the inflows of Chinese ICT services. However, the gap between these regions is starting to vanish. During this period, Czechia, Estonia, and Hungary noted not only the largest share of Chinese ICT services inflows to their manufacturing, but also the largest increase in this flow between 1995-

2020. In 2020, the same three economies realized the largest shares of Chinese servicification (Table 3, Table A).

Following the introduction of the BRI, European countries exhibited diverse responses in terms of servicification of manufacturing through Chinese ICT services. A subset of European economies experienced above-average increases in ICT servicification compared to the EU average, indicating a stronger engagement with Chinese digital services. Conversely, a similar number of economies recorded below-average growth rates, suggesting varying levels of integration of Chinese ICT services into their manufacturing sectors. Nonetheless, all European economies, except for Ireland, showed an increased dependency on Chinese ICT services post-BRI compared to the pre-BRI period, underscoring a broad trend of growing reliance on China in this domain. This heterogeneity in responses reflects differing national strategies, economic structures, and openness to Chinese digital service integration across Europe (Figure 7).

The analysis shows no evidence of decoupling between European manufacturing and Chinese ICT services, despite U.S. efforts. Since 2017, all European economies, except Ireland, have experienced an increase in the share of Chinese ICT services in manufacturing exports, with notable rises in Estonia post-Trump (Figure 7). This trend is consistent across Western Europe and CEE (Figure 8, Table A in the appendix). Although Chinese FDI in Europe declined due to geopolitical tensions, the inflow of Chinese ICT services into European manufacturing continued, driven by shifts in FDI towards the automotive and consumer sectors (Köncke and de Graaff, 2024; Rhodium Group, 2023).

Figure 7. Comparison of servicification of European manufacturing with Chinese ICT services in pre-BRI and post-BRI introduction and pre-Trump and post-Trump presidency (% of gross exports)

Axes intersect in values for China's average share of Europe's servicification with Chinese ICT from 1995 to 2020 (1.31%, 2.41%)

Axes intersect in values for China's average share of Europe's servicification with Chinese ICT from 1995 to 2020 (1.47%, 2.86%)

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

Figure 8. Servicification of European manufacturing with Chinese ICT services in 1995-2020 (% of gross exports)

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

Western Europe and CEE show similar median dependency levels on Chinese ICT, although Western Europe’s dependence is more variable (larger range), while CEE displays slightly greater stability. A significant rise in the servicification of manufacturing is seen in telecommunications, with more moderate growth in computer programming, consultancy, and information services (Figure 9). This pattern reflects China's deep involvement in GVCs and the development of its telecommunications sector (Figure 2). No decoupling is observed; instead, countries like Czechia show high and growing levels of dependency on Chinese ICT services, particularly post-Trump (Tables B and C in the appendix), highlighting continued integration of Chinese ICT in European manufacturing despite geopolitical pressures.

Figure 9. Servicification of European manufacturing with Chinese ICT subsectors in 1995 and 2020 (% of gross exports)

	Western Europe		CEE	Western Europe	CEE
	1995			2020	
Median	Telecommunication	0.93%	0.70%	5.91%	5.47%
	Computer programming...	0.78%	0.48%	2.41%	2.05%
Max	Telecommunication	1.44% (UK)	1.50% (Cyprus)	9.34% (Finland)	13.39% (Czechia)
	Computer programming...	1.18% (UK)	1.86% (Cyprus)	3.22% (Finland)	5.43% (Czechia)
Min	Telecommunication	0.65% (Austria)	0.34% (Latvia)	2.14% (Ireland)	4.05% (Cyprus)
	Computer programming...	0.41% (Austria)	0.28% (Latvia)	0.95% (Ireland)	1.43% (Lithuania)

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

If going the other way, the analysis of value-added flows between Europe and China reveals significant differences in these exchanges. While China's ICT value-added contribution to European economies, including CEE, has increased substantially, European ICT's contribution to Chinese manufacturing remains considerably larger, and this asymmetry is growing. Furthermore, there is a significant disparity in the dependence of Chinese manufacturing on Western Europe compared to CEE (Figures 8, 10, 11).

Again, the analysis of potential decoupling between Europe and China in advanced services shows no reduction in European ICT exports to Chinese manufacturing. Instead, there has been a notable increase in the integration of European ICT services into Chinese manufacturing processes in recent years (Figure 10). A closer look at individual European economies and regions also reveals no decline in servicification since the Trump presidency. Notably, Germany, a significant outlier in the pre-Trump era, continued its strong involvement, with overall engagement from Western Europe and CEE economies intensifying post-Trump (Figure 11). This highlights the enduring connection between Europe and China in ICT services despite geopolitical tensions.

Figure 10. Servicification of Chinese manufacturing with European ICT in 1995 and 2020 (% of gross exports)

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

Figure 11. Changes in servicification of Chinese manufacturing with European ICT

Pre-Trump Western Europe: median=0.67%; max=4.85% (Germany); min=0.01% (Iceland)

Pre-Trump CEE: median=0.03%; max=0.22% (Poland); min=0.01% (Latvia)

Post-Trump Western Europe: median=0.77%; max=6.65% (Germany); min=0.02% (Iceland)

Post-Trump CEE: median=0.07%; max=0.50% (Poland); min=0.03% (Latvia)

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

4.2. Servicification of most depended industries

The next phase of analyzing Europe's dependence on China in terms of servicification involves an examination of specific subsectors of manufacturing (Figure 12). Based on the intensity of inflows of Chinese ICT services and the degree of Europe's dependence (Table 1), six subsectors have been identified and divided into three groups. The first group consists of electronics and electrical products, including computer, electronic, and optical products; electrical equipment; and machinery and equipment n.e.c. The second group is related to the transportation sector, comprising motor vehicles, trailers, and semi-trailers and other transport equipment. The final subsector analyzed is textiles, wearing apparel, leather, and related products.

The first group experienced an increase in the intensity of Chinese ICT service inflows, both in Western Europe and CEE, which is often associated with Chinese investments in these European subsectors (Kratz et al., 2021; Joshi, 2019; Paulo, 2018). No European country reported a decline in dependency on China in these subsectors. Furthermore, comparing the medians for Western Europe and CEE, they were similar in both 1995 and 2020, with outliers predominantly appearing in CEE, whereas Western Europe showed less variation in dependence on China.

The highest dependence on Chinese ICT services was noted in the computer, electronic, and optical products subsector, with the European median share rising from 0.72% in 1995 to 4.70% in 2020. While the average share of Chinese ICT services was similar between Western Europe and CEE, there was greater variation within CEE. In 2020, the most significant outlier was Czechia (18.92%), which was also the most dependent on China across Europe. This high share of Chinese ICT services in Czech electronics is attributed not to Chinese FDI but to the characteristics of the Czech electronics industry, which relies heavily on imported materials, components, and parts for production and assembly. Approximately three-quarters of exports consist of imported components. In addition to Czechia, other CEE countries with high dependence on China in this subsector included Estonia, Poland, Hungary, and Slovakia, with similar levels of dependence (7.92%, 7.27%, 7.20%, and 7.19%, respectively). In Western Europe, Germany, Norway, and the Netherlands absorbed the most Chinese ICT services (5.92%, 6.34%, and 5.49%, respectively).

Subsectors electrical equipment and machinery and equipment n.e.c. exhibited patterns similar to the previous subsector. In 2020, in Western Europe, Germany, Spain, and Norway showed the highest dependence on Chinese ICT services (5.07%, 5.05%, and 4.98%, respectively). Among CEE countries, besides Czechia (11.37%), Malta and Slovakia displayed strong dependence on China (5.22% and 4.88%, respectively). For machinery and equipment

n.e.c., Czechia showed the strongest reliance on Chinese ICT services in 2020 (6.52%), followed by Spain and Sweden (4.51% and 4.35%, respectively). However, in this subsector, the difference in median values between Western Europe and CEE was the largest of the three discussed in this group (3.56% and 2.79%).

The next area of Europe's dependence on Chinese ICT services is the transportation sector, although the level of dependence here is lower than in the previously discussed group. However, this could change as China is increasingly interested in the global automotive industry (Ancarani et al., 2021), making substantial investments in Europe and developing its own industry (Kratz et al., 2021).

Both subsectors - motor vehicles, trailers, and semi-trailers and other transport equipment - showed similar low levels of dependence on China in 1995 for both Western Europe and CEE. However, by 2020, substantial increases and greater divergence between these two regions of Europe were observed. The largest recipients of Chinese FDI and ICT services in the transportation manufacturing sector are major automotive players like Germany, France, Spain, and Sweden, as well as select CEE countries. These economies are also the primary contributors to transport manufacturing enriched with Chinese ICT. There are also instances of short-term spikes in Chinese ICT inflows to other European economies, as seen in Greece's increasing dependence on Chinese ICT in other transport equipment. Although Greece previously played a negligible role, its share increased rapidly following China's acquisition of the port of Piraeus and significant FDI. In both subsectors, Western Europe exhibited greater dependence on Chinese ICT services than CEE in 2020 (3.41% versus 2.94% for motor vehicles, trailers, and semi-trailers and 3.59% versus 2.76% for other transport equipment). Northern Europe (Iceland, Finland, Norway) was the most dependent on Chinese ICT in the motor vehicles, trailers, and semi-trailers subsector in 2020, while the Czech Republic and Scandinavia dominated the other transport equipment subsector.

The only low-tech subsector among those studied, but one that is significantly dependent on Chinese ICT, is textiles, wearing apparel, leather, and related products. This subsector, like the others analyzed, experienced growth between 1995 and 2020, though the increase was smaller than in the other subsectors. This subsector also displayed significant variation between Western Europe and CEE. In 2020, the median for Western Europe was 4.46%, compared to 3.43% for CEE. The most dependent countries in 2020 were Spain, the UK, Slovenia, and Switzerland (7.94%, 6.02%, 5.95%, and 5.94%, respectively). The dependence of these countries on Chinese ICT is largely linked to the presence of certain Chinese clothing companies, such as Shanghai Jingqingrong Garment, in European markets, and the supply of

major European manufacturers (e.g., H&M) with products made in countries like Spain (Martinez, 2024).

Figure 12. Servicification of Western European (WE) and CEE manufacturing subsectors with Chinese ICT in 1995 and 2020 (% of gross exports)

Detailed parameters are in the appendix (Table D).

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

The analysis of servicification within individual subsectors does not support the hypothesis of decoupling. Instead, the data reveals the opposite trend—a marked increase in dependency, particularly within technologically advanced subsectors. This suggests a deepening integration between European manufacturing and Chinese ICT services, highlighting

the growing interdependence in key areas such as technological sectors, where reliance on Chinese ICT inputs has surged in recent years. The rising interconnection underscores the significant role that Chinese services play in supporting European manufacturing, even amidst broader geopolitical tensions (Table 2).

Table 2. Changes in shares of Chinese servicification in subsectors of European manufacturing pre- and post-Trump era

	Pre-Trump	Post-Trump
textiles, wearing apparel, leather and related products	7,45%	11,38%
computer, electronic and optical products	6,52%	13,80%
electrical equipment	6,47%	11,91%
machinery and equipment n.e.c.	5,29%	9,75%
motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	5,02%	9,33%
other transport equipment	5,31%	9,53%

Annual average share of gross exports.

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database, edition 2023.

Conclusions

The role of the Chinese economy in GVCs is strengthening and transforming. Currently, Chinese companies are moving towards services and business model improvements and focusing on digitalization (Chen et al., 2021, 2022; Zhang, 2019). A symptom of this novelty is the form of production servicing, which is expected to change the GVC landscape. By introducing various strategies to stimulate technological development, China has increasingly focused on the export of value added from advanced technologies, including ICT services.

The analysis of Sino-European relations in the context of ICT servicification reveals several key insights.

First, it proved the increased dependency on Chinese ICT services across all European economies analyzed. The growth is particularly pronounced in technologically advanced subsectors, where Chinese ICT services play a critical role in manufacturing processes. The data shows no evidence of decoupling, even in regions historically more resistant to globalization trends. The results of this study are consistent with the analyses conducted by Yu et al. (2023).

Second, there is a convergence between Western European and CEE economies. While Western Europe initially had a higher share of Chinese ICT services embedded in its gross exports, CEE economies have rapidly closed the gap. Both regions now exhibit similar levels

of dependence on Chinese ICT services, especially in key analysed subsectors such as automotive, electronics, and textiles.

Third, there is a limited impact of global shocks as decoupling. Servicification has proved to be little susceptible to any shocks, including decoupling. The U.S. efforts to decouple from China had no significant impact on European servicification trends, as most European countries maintained or increased their reliance on Chinese ICT services post-Trump. Also, in the manufacturing subsectors no signs of decoupling were found. On the contrary, Europe's dependence on Chinese services in these fields has steadily grown, underscoring the role of Chinese ICT services as vital components of European advanced manufacturing.

Fourth, BRI has also limited impact on servicification. While the post-BRI period was marked by increases in the inflow of Chinese value-added services, these rises appear to be part of broader trends rather than a direct result of BRI itself. The analysis indicates that the introduction of the BRI did not dramatically alter the trajectory of Chinese servicification in Europe, particularly when compared to earlier periods of globalization. At first sight, the result of the study seems to contradict numerous studies focused on the impact of BRI on GVCs in general (e.g. Zheng et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2024). However, studies specifically on technological GVCs are no longer conclusive (Pepe, 2021; Joshi, 2019).

Fifth, the study also revealed a significant asymmetry in the flow of ICT services between China and Europe, especially CEE. This means that companies from the CEE region do not massively export ICT services to the Chinese market because they either do not produce them and/or they are not service providers that can face the competition from Western European companies. However, the intense growth in the share of Chinese ICT services in manufacturing in CEE confirms the high demand for these services, which may still indicate poor development of the internal market for these services. Similar conclusions provided studies (Kordalska and Olczyk, 2021; Cieřlik, 2024b)

Finally, the inflows of Chinese ICT services to European manufacturing presented in the article show China's consistent strategy related to increasing its influence in the production of developed economies. Particularly visible is the focus of ICT service streams on industries that are key to China's development.

Basis on the results, several policy recommendations can be made.

First, Chinese policymakers should prioritize the expansion of their digital services sector in overseas markets, aligning more closely with global trends. This would secure China's position in global digital GVCs, in line with recommendations from Gao and Rong (2023) and

Kan et al. (2022), who suggest focusing on value-added services, specially advanced services, to ensure that servicification boosts competitiveness and profitability.

Second, policies promoting international collaboration, especially with European countries, could accelerate the transfer of digital technologies and best practices. This is supported by the work of Razzaq et al. (2021), who emphasize the importance of regulating cross-border digital services and taxation as part of future global economic policy. Such partnerships could help bring China's participation in GVCs up to global standards and further integrate it into international trade networks. All the above-mentioned activities and plans should have a long-term dimension.

Third, to reduce the asymmetry in ICT services trade between China and CEE, policymakers should negotiate broader access for CEE suppliers to the Chinese market, encouraging a more balanced flow of services (Gu, 2023; Köncke and d Graaff, 2024).

Fourth, Chinese policymakers should recognise the importance of balancing the growth of digital services at home and abroad. While services have been successfully integrated into domestic manufacturing as a whole, the uneven uptake of digital services across different domestic industries highlights the need for targeted policies that encourage digital transformation at home. At the same time, policies need to be put in place to enable better expansion of ICT services globally. This could include encouraging industries and regions that are lagging behind in the implementation of digital solutions in exports, and ensuring that technological advances are available to a wider range of sectors (Zhang et al., 2024).

The results from the study also provide two practical implications.

Firstly, the results indicate that although China has made significant progress in promoting traditional services within GVCs, its role in digital services in European markets remains limited. To take full advantage of the benefits of digitalisation, Chinese companies should prioritise strengthening the digital services sector in overseas markets. By doing so, China can secure a stronger position in global digital GVCs and reduce its reliance on traditional services by aligning itself more closely with global trends.

Second, as China continues its transition to a service-oriented economy, it needs to address the 'servicification paradox', in which investments in service integration are not delivering the expected returns (Brax et al., 2021). In a bid to mitigate or eliminate this risk, Chinese firms should focus on developing value-added services that complement their manufacturing base, rather than simply expanding their service offerings. This approach will help ensure that servicification increases competitiveness and profitability within GVCs and enhances China's role in the Europe.

In the end, there are also theoretical implications of the study.

The study reinforces the concept of digital servicification within GVCs, highlighting how ICT services are increasingly integrated into manufacturing processes. This supports existing literature on the digitalization of GVCs, which argues that technological advancements are reshaping traditional manufacturing sectors (Szalavetz, 2019; Awan et al., 2022). The findings reveal that China's strategic push toward digital services is consistent with broader trends in GVC transformation, emphasizing the importance of digital services as critical enablers of competitiveness and efficiency in global manufacturing.

The research provides empirical evidence of the increased dependence of European economies on Chinese ICT services, particularly in technologically advanced subsectors. This aligns with technology dependency theory, suggesting that the integration of advanced technologies into GVCs creates new forms of economic interdependence between countries (Se Gregori, 1978). The growing reliance on Chinese ICT services demonstrates how servicification can deepen dependencies, particularly in regions like CEE, which lack competitive domestic ICT sectors (Kordalska and Olczyk, 2021).

The observed convergence between Western and CEE economies in their dependency on Chinese ICT services highlights the shifting dynamics within European GVCs. This convergence challenges traditional GVC hierarchies and suggests that smaller or less developed economies can rapidly integrate into advanced segments of GVCs through digital servicification (Gölgeci et al., 2021). The increasing alignment in the use of Chinese ICT services across Europe may reflect a broader trend toward the democratization of access to advanced digital services within GVCs.

There are also a number of issues that are not addressed in the article, but are certainly worth further research. Simultaneously, the increasing share of Chinese services in European manufacturing, especially those related to cross-border data flows, forces an area for further research, which is the introduction of appropriate regulations and the interaction of state institutions with economic actors. This issue is very well discussed in the work of Chaisse (2023). Another problem with increased digitalisation is the taxation of digital services. (Chaisse, 2021). Another area for further exploration is Sino-European relations (also in terms of cross-sectoral linkages of GVCs) in relation to the phenomena of Asian regionalism and new economic agreements (Chaisse and Hsieh, 2023). Moreover, digital servicification is not only about dominance in technology production and trade, but also in the diffusion of technological ideas such as digital currency (Slawotsky, 2022).

In the end, there is a challenge regarding the long-term implications of the results obtained in this study. The analysis suggests that the GVCs under discussion have demonstrated resilience to shocks such as decoupling and have played an increasingly significant role in Sino-European relations. However, it is crucial to consider potential shifts in the European Parliament and the upcoming U.S. elections, both of which could lead to changes in policies toward China. Additionally, the prolonged Russian-Ukrainian conflict introduces considerable uncertainty in the future configuration of GVCs. Therefore, any assertion that the current trend of strengthening flows within these GVCs will continue should be approached with caution.

Acknowledgment

The author wishes to thank the anonymous reviewers for their insightful comments on the earlier draft. All opinions and any errors remain solely the author's own.

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Appendix

Table A. Servicification of European countries manufacturing with Chinese ICT services in 1995-2020 (% of gross exports)

	1995-1999	2000-2004	2005-2009	2010-2014	2015-2020	Pre-BRI (1995-2012)	Post-BRI (2013-2020)	Pre-Trump (1995-2016)	Post-Trump (2017-2020)	1995-2020
Austria	0,49	0,70	1,34	1,16	2,18	0,92	1,97	1,04	2,37	2,69
Belgium	0,66	0,76	1,53	1,18	1,44	0,99	1,34	1,02	1,51	2,26
Bulgaria	0,67	0,89	2,06	1,41	2,21	1,22	2,02	1,30	2,34	3,08
Croatia	0,35	0,65	1,68	1,34	1,76	1,02	1,64	1,09	1,87	2,54
Cyprus	0,95	1,43	1,76	2,24	1,77	1,36	1,59	1,35	1,91	2,91
Czechia	0,56	1,51	3,54	2,50	4,56	2,16	4,13	2,34	5,10	5,90
Denmark	0,71	0,86	1,49	2,44	2,81	1,13	2,55	1,30	3,03	3,41
Estonia	0,45	1,56	2,50	2,59	4,63	1,75	4,32	2,12	4,85	5,58
Finland	0,64	1,16	2,46	2,13	3,29	1,52	2,98	1,67	3,60	4,22
France	1,03	1,38	2,34	2,15	3,41	1,68	3,15	1,87	3,58	4,55
Germany	1,02	1,24	2,17	1,90	3,28	1,58	2,98	1,73	3,53	4,28
Greece	0,94	1,41	2,09	2,19	2,63	1,51	2,43	1,64	2,62	3,76
Hungary	0,69	2,53	3,71	2,61	3,25	2,41	2,99	2,42	3,54	5,29
Iceland	0,58	1,51	1,87	1,57	3,74	1,49	3,54	1,80	3,89	4,63
Ireland	0,54	0,77	1,75	1,37	0,75	0,94	0,71	0,87	0,85	1,70
Italy	0,85	1,22	2,23	1,78	3,16	1,55	2,93	1,74	3,26	4,21
Latvia	0,37	0,80	1,31	1,26	2,23	0,91	2,05	1,06	2,35	2,74
Lithuania	0,43	1,16	1,36	1,07	1,76	1,00	1,61	1,07	1,86	2,50
Luxembourg	0,80	0,52	1,23	1,22	1,47	0,87	1,36	0,92	1,56	2,13
Malta	0,63	0,85	1,31	1,44	2,43	0,99	2,23	1,17	2,50	2,99
Netherlands	0,58	0,77	1,22	1,50	2,71	0,95	2,40	1,12	2,92	3,07
Norway	0,62	0,88	1,55	1,83	2,60	1,09	2,38	1,25	2,76	3,22

Poland	0,98	1,28	2,39	1,66	3,10	1,63	2,87	1,80	3,20	4,26
Portugal	0,56	0,70	1,26	1,48	2,09	0,89	1,90	1,01	2,28	2,60
Romania	0,65	0,98	1,88	2,21	2,31	1,25	2,19	1,39	2,36	3,26
Slovakia	0,48	0,97	2,82	2,10	3,55	1,62	3,37	1,94	3,37	4,65
Slovenia	0,53	0,88	1,56	1,76	2,53	1,06	2,30	1,22	2,66	3,13
Spain	0,88	1,14	2,13	1,76	3,36	1,47	3,06	1,67	3,51	4,22
Sweden	0,51	0,71	1,27	1,42	3,20	0,92	2,82	1,13	3,59	3,38
Switzerland	0,57	0,72	1,17	1,71	2,28	0,89	2,09	1,03	2,49	2,74
United Kingdom	1,15	1,70	2,43	2,08	3,14	1,80	2,91	1,94	3,21	4,49
Western Europe	0,73	1,01	1,75	1,71	2,64	1,23	2,42	1,38	2,81	1,60
CEE	0,60	1,19	2,15	1,86	2,78	1,42	2,56	1,56	2,91	1,77

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database (2023 edition).

Table B. Servicification of European countries manufacturing with Chinese telecommunication services in 1995-2020 (% of gross exports)

	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Austria	0,65	0,60	0,92	0,86	0,78	0,90	1,03	1,04	1,33	1,53	1,83	2,21	2,43	2,97	2,64	2,71	2,51	2,97	2,77	3,26	3,81	3,85	3,98	4,77	4,97	5,36
Belgium	0,86	0,88	1,08	1,08	1,00	0,99	1,02	1,11	1,44	1,69	2,27	2,76	3,74	3,33	2,46	1,94	2,00	2,40	2,18	2,49	2,96	2,86	2,78	3,41	3,47	3,55
Czechia	0,54	0,59	0,89	1,07	1,04	1,16	1,53	1,88	3,73	3,66	4,18	4,83	6,11	6,98	7,58	7,69	7,03	6,67	5,40	5,98	6,82	6,20	6,41	7,97	9,97	13,39
Denmark	1,09	0,88	0,99	1,07	1,01	1,11	1,19	1,28	1,61	1,70	2,24	2,72	2,84	3,27	3,24	3,27	3,42	4,37	3,87	4,45	5,25	4,93	4,99	5,96	6,02	6,14
Estonia	0,58	0,44	0,58	0,65	0,75	1,10	2,13	2,59	2,51	2,63	4,01	4,19	4,14	3,96	3,67	4,42	5,50	6,39	5,49	6,13	7,05	6,97	7,27	8,40	8,37	8,23
Finland	0,81	0,65	0,83	1,06	1,04	1,22	1,47	1,75	2,76	3,20	4,15	5,79	5,07	5,16	4,64	4,78	3,93	6,20	5,14	6,08	6,99	7,11	7,17	8,67	8,85	9,34
France	1,23	1,35	1,67	1,68	1,55	1,61	1,84	1,93	2,56	3,08	3,62	3,83	3,86	4,15	4,04	4,21	3,77	4,21	4,03	4,64	5,42	5,38	5,54	6,68	6,89	6,29
Germany	1,43	1,49	1,65	1,68	1,57	1,61	1,81	1,92	2,56	3,09	3,41	4,04	4,52	4,64	4,13	4,55	3,98	4,14	3,87	4,57	5,53	5,58	5,85	6,87	7,04	7,73
Greece	1,05	1,18	1,37	1,65	1,38	1,69	2,10	2,23	2,26	2,41	3,14	3,06	4,00	3,89	3,00	2,58	2,75	2,97	2,53	2,57	3,94	3,98	3,30	4,08	4,01	4,01

Hungary	0,76	0,78	1,14	1,47	1,60	2,00	3,09	4,50	6,74	5,44	7,07	6,72	6,72	7,44	7,52	7,94	6,02	5,73	4,86	5,22	5,66	5,58	5,88	6,89	7,29	8,78
Iceland	0,76	0,69	0,66	0,69	0,71	0,78	2,82	2,20	2,80	1,74	2,21	2,66	3,09	3,87	3,55	3,39	3,20	5,92	5,19	5,21	6,05	5,70	5,27	7,34	7,25	6,75
Ireland	0,81	0,82	0,89	0,97	0,51	0,40	0,68	0,94	1,76	2,47	3,24	4,52	3,58	2,66	1,52	1,17	1,00	1,47	1,43	1,67	1,45	1,39	1,41	2,37	1,58	2,14
Italy	1,42	1,12	1,26	1,33	1,25	1,53	1,54	1,84	2,24	2,62	3,02	3,83	4,22	5,07	3,82	4,11	4,06	4,05	3,80	4,47	5,29	5,08	4,78	5,84	5,92	6,28
Latvia	0,34	0,31	0,44	0,70	0,58	0,72	0,74	1,09	1,28	1,49	1,70	2,02	2,58	2,54	2,01	2,10	2,59	2,97	3,08	3,38	3,99	3,58	3,90	4,33	4,50	4,82
Lithuania	0,45	0,41	0,52	0,58	0,50	1,06	1,24	1,52	2,04	1,75	1,66	1,90	1,97	2,28	2,66	2,07	2,08	2,40	2,21	2,32	3,04	3,01	2,89	3,57	3,74	4,24
Luxembourg	1,26	1,35	1,49	1,61	0,57	0,50	0,53	0,62	0,91	1,18	1,19	1,86	1,66	2,59	3,56	1,88	1,46	3,06	2,73	2,79	3,23	3,24	2,99	4,00	4,11	4,13
Netherlands	0,92	0,88	1,08	1,15	0,92	1,11	1,24	1,29	1,53	1,72	2,10	2,32	2,21	2,31	2,41	2,81	2,73	3,35	3,27	3,61	5,25	5,20	5,19	6,33	6,51	6,81
Norway	0,94	0,70	0,82	0,93	0,88	0,90	1,00	1,48	1,72	2,00	2,36	2,79	3,15	3,22	2,84	2,95	2,82	3,50	3,24	3,66	4,37	4,29	4,27	5,19	5,26	5,68
Poland	1,03	1,20	1,42	1,46	1,24	1,26	1,64	2,18	2,82	2,87	3,45	4,20	4,78	5,36	5,06	5,43	4,45	4,70	4,53	5,58	6,37	6,31	6,34	6,67	7,04	7,75
Portugal	0,80	0,77	0,84	0,85	0,75	0,91	0,95	1,05	1,17	1,27	1,56	2,08	2,32	2,54	1,88	2,36	1,88	2,21	2,16	2,53	3,06	2,99	3,02	3,78	4,12	4,67
Slovak Republic	0,54	0,58	0,76	0,79	0,86	1,01	1,20	1,38	1,79	2,25	3,36	4,11	5,17	6,00	5,08	5,28	4,70	5,02	5,16	6,19	6,82	7,14	7,38	6,00	5,87	6,30
Slovenia	0,70	0,52	0,85	0,95	0,96	0,96	1,11	1,26	1,66	1,98	2,29	2,69	2,82	2,97	2,51	2,99	2,81	3,16	2,79	3,60	4,26	4,01	4,02	4,81	4,94	5,47
Spain	1,21	1,08	1,34	1,44	1,40	1,46	1,53	1,65	2,03	2,34	2,90	3,59	4,21	4,27	3,34	3,76	3,18	3,41	3,70	4,21	5,41	5,33	5,32	6,10	6,26	6,73
Sweden	0,84	0,66	0,70	0,75	0,71	0,83	0,96	1,00	1,34	1,52	1,82	2,33	2,51	2,41	2,26	2,14	2,34	3,29	3,02	3,36	4,35	4,26	4,23	5,08	5,31	5,41
Switzerland	0,76	0,80	0,88	0,96	0,86	0,94	0,99	1,08	1,29	1,48	1,66	1,95	2,10	2,04	2,20	2,18	1,89	2,58	2,50	2,84	3,29	3,21	3,50	4,56	4,66	5,29
United Kingdom	1,44	1,52	1,73	1,87	1,72	2,04	2,46	2,66	3,11	3,41	3,83	4,50	4,50	4,74	4,14	4,33	3,75	4,39	4,16	5,28	6,36	6,17	5,82	6,90	6,91	8,17
Bulgaria	0,90	0,97	0,74	0,87	0,87	0,84	1,02	1,08	1,48	1,74	2,37	2,53	3,93	4,14	3,55	2,65	2,47	2,54	2,48	3,13	3,72	3,61	3,72	4,55	4,63	4,83
Croatia	0,46	0,43	0,53	0,56	0,52	0,58	0,98	1,11	1,34	1,59	2,12	2,93	3,26	3,63	3,27	3,58	3,30	3,70	2,57	2,75	3,46	3,20	3,35	3,83	3,77	4,21
Cyprus	1,50	0,95	0,98	1,30	1,44	1,83	2,03	1,99	2,35	2,03	1,85	2,27	2,86	3,78	2,57	2,98	2,31	2,40	2,24	2,56	2,97	3,08	3,09	3,77	3,94	4,05
Malta	0,98	0,96	0,98	1,00	1,06	1,18	1,25	1,31	1,59	1,47	1,52	2,34	2,18	2,75	2,92	2,04	1,79	2,18	2,23	2,94	3,77	3,69	3,42	4,46	4,30	4,87
Romania	0,95	0,82	0,86	1,01	0,81	0,82	1,16	1,36	1,83	2,25	2,50	3,27	3,60	3,25	3,28	3,67	2,94	4,98	4,91	5,47	6,74	6,12	5,91	7,41	7,47	7,21

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database (2023 edition).

Table C. Servicification of European countries manufacturing with Chinese computer programming, consultancy, and information service activities in 1995-2020 (% of gross exports)

	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Austria	0,41	0,44	0,57	0,43	0,45	0,54	0,58	0,56	0,60	0,77	0,93	1,08	0,86	1,15	0,83	0,77	0,82	0,54	0,76	0,94	1,23	1,40	1,60	2,05	2,02	2,03
Belgium	0,77	0,63	0,68	0,50	0,52	0,51	0,55	0,56	0,60	0,73	0,91	0,95	0,83	0,94	0,65	0,53	0,59	0,32	0,47	0,61	0,76	0,81	0,91	1,19	1,17	1,17
Czechia	0,43	0,54	0,67	0,53	0,53	0,63	0,76	1,07	1,91	2,02	2,23	2,49	2,87	3,36	3,08	2,90	2,54	1,55	1,81	2,02	2,55	2,67	2,99	3,72	4,47	5,43
Denmark	0,79	0,98	0,80	0,54	0,54	0,63	0,71	0,78	0,81	0,88	1,08	1,08	0,87	1,17	0,94	0,99	1,37	0,72	0,94	1,24	1,70	1,85	2,10	2,78	2,72	2,76
Estonia	0,48	0,43	0,57	0,47	0,53	0,79	1,64	2,00	1,57	1,63	2,45	2,11	1,62	1,82	1,44	1,85	2,14	1,56	2,25	2,53	3,00	3,50	4,14	4,39	3,83	3,76
Finland	0,74	0,45	1,29	1,01	0,54	0,80	0,88	0,93	1,22	1,39	1,73	2,21	1,82	1,96	1,75	1,43	1,60	0,87	1,06	1,37	1,84	2,07	2,38	3,08	3,11	3,22
France	1,10	1,17	1,24	0,88	0,92	1,01	1,05	1,04	1,31	1,70	2,02	1,87	1,67	2,01	1,55	1,48	1,39	0,90	1,40	1,72	2,13	2,46	2,71	3,30	3,11	2,52
Germany	1,10	1,10	1,02	0,74	0,78	0,81	0,85	0,88	1,04	1,26	1,43	1,58	1,57	1,66	1,34	1,48	1,53	0,95	1,28	1,61	2,05	2,30	2,55	3,27	3,14	3,22
Greece	0,91	1,00	1,04	0,92	0,88	1,12	1,31	1,30	1,16	1,30	1,75	1,37	1,18	1,39	1,01	1,01	1,21	0,69	1,11	1,50	1,95	2,05	1,87	2,54	2,35	2,20
Hungary	0,41	0,56	0,65	0,65	0,85	1,13	1,56	2,15	2,93	2,41	2,94	2,79	2,72	2,99	2,39	2,62	1,78	1,12	1,40	1,53	1,82	2,10	2,45	2,94	2,87	3,07
Iceland	0,82	0,81	0,71	0,55	0,58	0,67	2,16	1,41	1,60	1,06	1,28	1,22	0,96	1,20	0,85	0,86	1,01	0,66	1,11	1,33	1,73	1,76	1,95	2,75	2,50	2,41
Ireland	0,73	0,71	0,63	0,50	0,45	0,42	0,48	0,58	0,95	1,37	1,65	2,25	1,88	1,53	0,76	0,49	0,38	0,30	0,50	0,59	0,46	0,53	0,58	1,09	0,76	0,95
Italy	0,85	0,82	0,88	0,67	0,69	0,90	0,89	0,97	1,04	1,32	1,49	1,55	1,32	1,58	1,14	1,28	1,28	0,74	1,14	1,51	1,91	2,00	2,11	2,61	2,44	2,44
Latvia	0,28	0,36	0,42	0,48	0,46	1,11	0,63	0,75	0,77	0,91	1,03	0,97	0,83	0,92	0,80	0,75	0,97	0,53	0,78	0,95	1,33	1,45	1,69	2,00	1,89	1,92
Lithuania	0,56	0,61	0,83	0,57	0,48	1,03	1,15	1,22	1,34	1,20	1,20	1,16	0,88	0,96	0,94	0,71	0,66	0,38	0,58	0,73	1,00	1,06	1,18	1,50	1,40	1,43
Luxembourg	0,96	0,99	0,95	0,75	0,32	0,36	0,38	0,45	0,61	0,64	0,60	0,78	0,64	1,00	1,16	0,71	0,61	0,34	0,41	0,52	0,73	0,79	0,89	1,27	1,29	1,37
Netherlands	0,62	0,51	0,57	0,46	0,41	0,55	0,65	0,66	0,68	0,86	0,96	1,01	0,79	0,79	0,72	0,86	0,86	0,48	0,70	0,94	1,45	1,59	1,94	2,45	2,36	2,32
Norway	0,57	0,70	0,71	0,51	0,52	0,56	0,60	0,74	0,71	0,88	1,07	1,11	0,92	1,11	0,81	0,79	0,91	0,62	0,95	1,18	1,57	1,79	1,97	2,49	2,38	2,40
Poland	1,07	1,41	1,23	0,98	0,88	0,84	0,86	0,99	1,11	1,22	1,45	1,61	1,46	1,83	1,40	1,40	1,11	0,74	1,13	1,48	1,85	2,11	2,24	2,45	2,39	2,39
Portugal	0,50	0,56	0,60	0,55	0,49	0,61	0,59	0,57	0,59	0,74	0,90	0,99	0,87	1,06	0,68	0,74	0,68	0,45	0,70	0,88	1,14	1,25	1,48	1,88	1,99	2,06
Slovak Republic	0,38	0,51	0,52	0,40	0,45	0,56	0,66	0,77	0,88	1,19	1,81	2,13	2,51	2,64	1,71	1,88	1,67	1,17	1,74	2,12	2,62	3,39	3,74	2,53	2,24	2,16
Slovenia	0,43	0,39	0,52	0,44	0,48	0,49	0,60	0,65	0,76	0,96	1,20	1,15	1,00	1,13	0,81	0,80	0,73	0,53	0,77	1,15	1,49	1,63	1,83	2,18	2,01	2,05
Spain	0,78	0,78	0,90	0,71	0,77	0,80	0,84	0,88	0,98	1,20	1,50	1,59	1,28	1,67	1,14	1,26	1,21	0,71	1,17	1,49	2,02	2,23	2,45	2,98	2,89	2,84
Sweden	0,61	0,58	0,52	0,41	0,40	0,50	0,94	0,58	0,58	0,75	1,01	1,02	0,86	0,86	0,79	0,77	1,11	0,71	0,91	1,17	1,68	1,81	1,96	2,62	2,69	2,68

Switzerland	0,56	0,64	0,69	0,56	0,56	0,65	0,65	0,66	0,72	0,90	0,92	1,10	1,05	1,03	1,09	0,96	0,87	0,68	1,08	1,22	1,49	1,63	1,90	2,46	2,28	2,34
United Kingdom	1,18	1,22	1,27	1,06	1,11	1,35	1,36	1,38	1,50	1,65	1,92	1,87	1,46	1,58	1,15	1,17	1,09	0,69	1,07	1,42	1,79	1,91	2,05	2,43	2,29	2,42
Bulgaria	0,85	0,89	0,66	0,64	0,65	0,66	0,71	0,73	0,90	1,15	1,56	1,45	1,53	1,64	1,21	0,66	0,75	0,46	0,72	0,97	1,25	1,33	1,48	1,94	1,79	1,72
Croatia	0,42	0,42	0,38	0,28	0,26	0,30	0,42	0,49	0,51	0,65	0,86	1,04	0,99	1,14	0,98	1,00	0,93	0,63	0,69	0,73	0,94	1,09	1,32	1,47	1,42	1,46
Cyprus	1,86	1,13	0,98	0,91	1,04	1,35	1,41	1,47	1,47	1,41	1,42	1,47	1,29	1,61	1,07	1,01	1,10	0,52	0,65	0,84	1,13	1,24	1,39	1,93	1,92	2,00
Malta	0,49	0,55	0,56	0,47	0,59	0,74	0,68	0,79	0,73	0,79	0,79	0,95	0,74	0,94	0,78	0,94	0,86	0,61	0,94	1,29	1,72	1,76	1,62	2,24	1,94	2,10
Romania	0,67	0,76	0,79	0,69	0,59	0,61	0,73	0,78	0,94	1,15	1,45	1,55	1,00	1,22	1,15	1,00	0,80	0,50	0,65	0,79	1,05	1,16	1,31	1,62	1,52	1,58

Source: based on OECD's ICIO Database (2023 edition).

Table D. Servicification of Western European and CEE manufacturing subsectors with Chinese ICT in 1995 and 2020 (% of gross exports)

		Western Europe	CEE	Western Europe	CEE
		1995		2020	
Median	computer, electronic and optical products	0.77%	0.48%	4.72%	4.61%
	electrical equipment	0.85%	0.46%	4.09%	3.79%
	machinery and equipment n.e.c.	0.75%	0.45%	3.56%	2.79%
	motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	0.71%	0.41%	3.41%	2.94%
	other transport equipment	0.84%	0.50%	3.59%	2.76%
	textiles, wearing apparel, leather and related products	1.39%	0.67%	4.46%	3.43%
Min	computer, electronic and optical products	0.00% (Iceland)	0.00% (Latvia)	1.79% (Luxembourg)	2.78% (Croatia)
	electrical equipment	0.00% (Iceland)	0.00% (Latvia)	1.10% (Ireland)	2.64% (Romania)
	machinery and equipment n.e.c.	0.37% (Iceland)	0.00% (Latvia)	1.38% (Ireland)	2.15% (Cyprus)
	motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	0.00% (Luxembourg)	0.00% (Latvia)	1.15% (Ireland)	2.07% (Lithuania)
	other transport equipment	0.00% (Iceland)	0.00% (Estonia)	1.17% (Ireland)	0.00% (Cyprus)
	textiles, wearing apparel, leather and related products	0.77% (Austria)	0.37% (Latvia)	0.99% (Ireland)	0.00% (Cyprus)
Max	computer, electronic and optical products	1.27% (France)	1.90% (Cyprus)	6.34% (Norway)	18.92% (Czechia)
	electrical equipment	1.31% (Germany)	1.98% (Cyprus)	5.08% (Sweden)	11.37% (Czechia)
	machinery and equipment n.e.c.	1.19% (United Kingdom)	1.27% (Cyprus)	4.51% (Spain)	6.52% (Czechia)
	motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	1.20% (United Kingdom)	1.61% (Cyprus)	5.13% (Iceland)	3.93% (Czechia)
	other transport equipment	2.44% (Germany)	2.33% (Poland)	5.13% (Iceland)	6.95% (Czechia)

	textiles, wearing apparel, leather and related products	2.70% (Iceland)	3.16% (Cyprus)	7.94% (Spain)	5.95% (Slovenia)
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